

A Study on the Change in Tax Policy with Reference to Interim Budget 2019

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Rohini Priyadharsana, A. "A Study on the Change in Tax Policy with Reference to Interim Budget 2019." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 8–11.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595694>

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Abstract

India is the sixth largest and fastest growing economy in the world. It has some advantages and responsibilities to equitably share the rewards of growth with its citizens. The interim Budget presented by the Union Finance Minister Piyush Goyal got a positive nod from almost all sectors as he delivered a high octane budget(although interim) that fulfilled the aspirations of common men and women who silently supported the building of Indian economy over the years. The interim Budget aimed at benefiting three major segments of the population- the farmers, informal sector workers and salaried tax payers. This paper analyses the interim budget and the tax policy framed to benefit small investors, individual tax payers and the middle class of our society by providing unexpected tax rebate.

Keywords: TDS threshold, tax concession, fiscal deficit, direct tax revenues, dimensions.

Introduction

In a major election year our country has seen its 15th Interim Budget presented by the Interim Finance Minister Piyush Goyal. He delivered the longest Interim Budget speech of 1.42 hours in the absence of Finance Minister Arun Jaitley who was away on medical leave. Goyal's Interim Budget is 'interim' only in name, for it includes tax give away which mandate a change in the Finance Bill which will continue into the next government and the next Budget. There are few governments that desist from using the Budget for their immediate political ends particularly at the eve of elections. In this backdrop, it is not surprising that the Interim Budget finds itself making a number of far reaching announcements that tried to lure atleast three big sections of the society-the farmers, the unorganized sectors and the more influential middle class.

Objective

The primary objective of this paper is to study, understand and analyze the change in tax policy by comparing with past Budget estimates. The secondary objective is to have an outlook of the benefits of interim budget to common people.

Research Methodology

The methodology is secondary with descriptive study and the research tools include Newspapers, Magazines and websites.

Interim Budget and the Tax Proposal

There have been two important changes that will reduce the tax outgo for a common man.

1. Individual taxpayers rebate
2. Standard deduction

The interim Budget contains several proposals aimed at reducing the tax burden on the salaried class and the home owners by increasing the tax rebate limit and amount for small taxpayers.

Section 87A of the Income Tax Act

The Income Tax Act, which was brought into force in 1961, is the statute under which all matters relating to taxation in India are listed. It includes levy, administration, collection as well as recovery of income tax. Section 87A, one of the several sections of the Income Tax Act, was inserted by the Finance Act, 2013, to provide tax relief to individual taxpayers. Rebate under Section 87A provides for a lower tax payment from individuals earning below a specified limit.

The stand in Finance Minister proposed amending Section 87A of the Income Tax Act to increase the rebate for taxpayers at the lower end of the spectrum. At present the section provides for a rebate of Rs 2500 for all taxpayers with income of less than Rs 3.5lakh a year. But the interim Budget raised the rebate amount to Rs 5lakh a year. This means that those earning upto Rs 5 lakh a year will be exempted from paying tax.

Section 80C of the Income Tax Act

Among the various tax-saving options, most individuals prefer to claim tax deduction under Section 80C of the Income Tax Act, 1961. Section 80C allows individuals and HUFs to claim tax deduction of up to Rs. 1,50,000 from their gross total income for certain investments and payments. Its instruments are of three broad kinds-expenditure based (such as home loan principal repayments), insurance based and investment based (includes long term bank and Post office deposits, EPF, PPF, NPS and equity linked savings schemes). The limit remained at Rs1,00,000 until 2014-15 and was increased by 50% to Rs1,50,000. The current interim budget follows the same where the people earning upto Rs 6,50,000 a year will not have to pay tax if they make full use of the deductible investments. This will provide tax benefit of Rs18, 500 crore to an estimated 3 crore middle class tax payers comprising self employed, small business. Small traders, pensioners and senior citizens.

Revised Standard Deduction

Standard deduction allows salaried individuals to claim a flat deduction from income towards expenses that would be incurred with relation to his or her employment. There is no proof required in order to claim this deduction. Standard deduction was introduced for the salaried taxpayers under Section 16 of the Income Tax Act in the year 1974, but later abolished with effect from Assessment Year 2006-07. This decision to withdraw standard deduction by former Union Minister of Finance P. Chidambaram was taken on the grounds that there laid an equivalent increase in the basic exemption limit and Section 80C deductions. The interim Budget has raised the standard deduction of salaried persons from Rs 40,000 to Rs50, 000 a year.

**The Table below Explains the Impact of
Tax Slap and Tax Reduced After Standard Deduction**

Individual current income (in Rs)	Tax rate	Less tax (in Rs)
0-2,50,000	Nil	Nil
2,50,000-5,00,000*	5%	520
5,00,000-1,00,00,000	20%	2080
Above 1,00,00,000	30%	3120

*Tax rebate of Rs 12,500 upto Rs 5, 00,000

Section 54 of the Income Tax Act

Section 54 of the Income Tax Act provides the seller of a residential property with relief from capital gains tax, if the proceeds from the sale are used to acquire another residential property. As per the current laws if the taxpayer owns more than one house property for personal use the rest of the properties are considered as deemed let out. Therefore the owner of a second house had to declare a notional rent (based on the prevalent rates in the specific neighborhood) in the income tax returns, though he could never receive the amount. This amount was taxed. For the next fiscal (starting April 1, 2019) this concept of notional rent is done away with. Therefore the owner of a second house from which no rent is received will not have to declare such an income or pay tax on it. For those with home loans on the second property is more attractive.

Example: If a person paid interest on home loan of Rs 2.5lakh annually and had to show a deemed rent of Rs 1 lakh per annum the net tax deduction would only be Rs1.5 lakh. With the latest Budget proposal in the above example the person can avail deduction of upto Rs 2 lakh, which is the upper threshold allowed

For making more homes available under affordable housing, the benefits under Section 80-1BA of the income tax act is being extended for one year (i.e.) housing projects approved till 31 March,2020. The TDS threshold for deduction of tax on rent has also been proposed to be increased from Rs1,80,000 to Rs 2,40,000.

House Property Income

Properties Owned by the taxpayer for self-use not let out	Current	Proposed
1	No Tax	No Tax
2	Property 1-no tax Property 2-tax on notional rent	No Tax
3	Property 1-no tax Property 2 & 3 -tax on notional rent	Property 1&2-no tax Property 3-tax on notional rent

TDS Threshold for Small Depositors

In a move designed to provide tax relief to those who prefer to save rather to invest the Budget contains the provision to increase threshold on interest earned on bank and post office from Rs.10,000 to Rs. 40,000 a year. Small Investors can heave a sigh of relief as the Budget has increased the threshold limit for TDS. The increase in TDS threshold in the interim budget will help people with no taxable income but who are supposed to file the Income Tax Return by submitting Form 15G or 15H to the institution deducting taxes (or) obtain a certificate (or)lower(or)Nil tax deduction from Income Tax Department.

Exempted Tax Payers

The tax payers earning more than Rs 5 lakh will not be eligible for this and have to pay tax according to normal rates. If a taxpayer with earnings higher than Rs 5 lakh wishes to get the rebate benefit then he should make investments and incur expenses that give tax breaks and try to bring their taxable income to Rs 5 lakh or below

Example: Say a taxpayer’s gross income after revised standard deduction of Rs 50,000 is Rs7.5lakh.If he invests

Section 80c instruments	- Rs 1.5 lakh
National Pension Scheme (NPS)	- Rs 50,000
Health insurance premium for himself	- Rs 25,000
Health insurance premium for his Parents	- Rs 25,000
Total	-Rs 2, 50,000

The taxable income comes down to Rs 5 lakh. He then becomes eligible for the rebate benefit under Budget 2019 and ends up paying no tax. The other expenses that can reduce taxable income include interest on home loan and on education loan.

Less Taxing Due to More Revenues

Any government may come forward to propose such a tax rebate only if there more revenue from its people. The current year shows a faster growth in the collection of Direct taxes whereas the indirect tax receipts remain steady. Direct taxes include Corporation tax, taxes on income (including cess, surcharge etc), and wealth and gift tax. It is also a fact that there was an increase in the share of personal income tax when compared to the corporate tax. The table below explains the revenues that resulted in an unexpected tax rebate.

Rupee comes from	In paisa
Borrowings and other liabilities	19
Corporation tax	21
Income tax	17
Customs	4
Goods and Service Tax	7
Non tax revenue	8
Non –Dept capital receipt	3

Demonetization, GST and other steps towards formalization increased the tax base and it follows that tax rates can themselves be cut. Tax receipts have grown from 10% of GDP, a level at which they had stagnated since the cuts after the global financial crisis to 12%. Although the GST has not yet resulted in the rise in indirect tax ratios above 5.5%, it is likely to do so as it stabilizes. The transfer to farmers and tax cuts amount to only 0.4% of GDP this year and are partially funded by a 0.3% rise in tax ratio. The move to exempt the lower income bracket (< Rs 5 lakh) has been done because of the soaring revenues from personal income tax over the last decade and a half.

Conclusion

The major tax reforms undertaken by the government led to the increase in tax collection and tax base. It induced the government to pass some benefits from the tax reforms to the middle class tax payers. It makes good economic sense to move towards a system of wider base and lower rates. Though the revenue growth backed in FY15 as well as FY16 it came back on the track from FY17 with growth of 13% and 12% in FY17 and FY18 respectively. The Budget seeks to put more money in the hands of middle class but disappointed as it left corporation tax rate untouched. The Ten Dimensions laid out by the stand in Finance Minister as Vision 2030 made the interim budget more attractive and strong. It's evident that only by prompt payment of Income tax the Citizens of India can enjoy more tax rebate in the near future.

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